

Contribution of The Catholic Church to Instructional Resources and Appointment of School Administrators in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya. A study across Public Secondary Schools in Kisii Central Sub - County

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ABSTRACT: Kenya's Legislation on Basic Education directs religious sponsors to participate in appointment of principals and provision of instructional materials to schools. In Kisii Central Sub-County, the Catholic Church participates in management of 29(39.7%) secondary schools. However, queries were being raised on the current contribution of the church as it had come to the fore that most sponsored schools were experiencing crises that had tended to be linked to the church's participation in school management. For instance, out of 29 principals in the sub-county, 18 (62.07%) new principals; 23 (79.31%) deputy principals and 5 (17.24%) BOM chair persons were rejected by the church from assuming their positions between 2010 - 2013 in the Sub-County which was higher compared to neighbouring Sub-Counties, that is, Marani 1(4.54%) and Kisii South 2 (7.41%) Principals; while Masaba 3 (12%) and Sameta 3 (13.04%) both involving Board of Management. The objectives of the study were to establish the contribution of Catholic Church to instructional resources and to find out the contribution of the Catholic Church in appointment of school administrators to management positions of public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. The findings of this study indicated that the Catholic Church contribution to instructional resources was 50.8% in terms of laboratory equipment, text books and teaching materials and appointment of school administrators was 25%. This had positive influence on management Quality Index.

KEY WORDS: Contribution, The Catholic Church, Instructional Resources, Appointment of Administrators, Public Secondary Schools, Kenya. A study across Public Secondary Schools, Kisii Central Sub - County.

INTRODUCTION

During the eighteenth century, the clergy managed education in Kenya. They built new schools, financed them, recruited and trained teachers, oversaw the implementation of the curriculum, taught catechism and approved new teaching approaches (Republic of Kenya, 1994). On the other hand the state supported the churches by granting land and dispensing annual subsidies to support the Native missions. By 1920, the missionaries were increasingly committed to education not only to meet the demands of converts but also forestall any attempts by the government to monopolize education (Sheffield, 2009). Overtime, the government set up their own schools; to promote the colonial segregation policy for the Europeans, Asians and Africans as per the Fraser Commission, 1909. The Churches used Corresponding schools they had set up as an evangelizing medium, while the government initiated schools were run on secular basis (Sheffield, 2009). At independence in 1963; the Kenyan government recognized the role played by church missionaries in the promotion of education. The schools that were established by the church remained under the sponsorship of those churches but registered as public schools.

After independence the new Kenyan government through an Act of Parliament passed the Education Act in 1968. The Education Act required that the Church hand over the management of schools to the local authority, Chapter 211:8 (3) and assume the role of a sponsor. In 1969 as the Education Act was being implemented, Pope John Paul VI created the Catholic Diocese of Kisii. From then on the Catholic Diocese of Kisii took part in implementation of the Education Act and continued to play a role in provision of Education. This research intends to carry out a case study of Kisii Catholic Diocese role in the provision of education in general and in particular secondary education with a view of finding out what contributions the Catholic Church has made and how its work can be strengthened, so that the church can achieve its basic mission of evangelizing through education. The Basic Education Act 2013

provides for the role of the religious sponsors in management of schools that they sponsor. These includes appointment of principals, financial support, provision of instructional resources, infrastructure development and Guidance and Counseling services to teaching staff, non teaching staff and students. It is for this reason that majority for Boards of management members are those nominated by the sponsor in relation to other positions of representation.

In Kisii Central Sub - County, however, doubts had been raised regarding its contribution to public secondary school management. Out of 29 schools, 18 new principals representing 62.07%, 23 deputy principals which was 79.31% and 5 BOM chair persons (17.24%) had been rejected by the church between 2010 and 2013 in the Sub - County (SCDE, 2013). The above figures were very alarming compared to the neighbouring Sub-Counties that had experienced far much less cases. For example, Marani had only 1(4.54%) case and Kisii South had 2 (7.41%) cases, both involving principals; while Masaba Sub-County reported 3 (12%) and Sameta Sub-County had 3 (13.04%) cases and both involving BOM chair persons over the same period. There was very scanty documented information on the contributions of the Church in Educational Institutions currently, from the SCDE's office. The problem has been a major cause of conflicts between the sponsors and other education stakeholders and this has raised questions on its contribution to the low academic performance in the Sub - County as well as the entire Gusii land as a region.

SYNTHESIS OF LITERATURE ON CONTRIBUTION OF THE CATHOLIC CHURCH TO INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

In England and Wales, there have been considerable changes to the way the money has been collected to the support of Catholic schools. The money towards the Catholic community in regards to learning materials and supporting schools has risen from 50% to 90% in both England and Wales. In 2009, Catholic schools in England comprised two-thirds of all religious secondary schools (Neal, 2008).

In Turkey, the plight of the Syrian Orthodox in Midyat flies in the face of AK's efforts to improve the treatment of Christians. Greater freedom for non-Muslim minorities is among the European Union's main demands on Turkey, which is hoping to join. The government has made a string of gestures: restoring an Armenian church in Van and opening it to worship (if only once); giving free Armenian-language textbooks out in schools; and sending out orders from Recep Tayyip Erdogan, the prime minister, that Christians must not be ill-treated. None of this impresses Samuel Aktas, the bishop in charge of Mor Gabriel. He has vowed to take his case to the European Court of Human Rights. "I have remained silent in the face of these injustices; but no longer so," he declares. All this is meant to boost confidence of Christian children in schools (Fagan, 2010).

According to Ouya and Mweseli (2015), Catholic schools have been in the forefront of education in Rwanda, a country of more than 50 percent Catholics. After the 1994 Rwanda Genocide that took close to one million innocent lives, including priests, nuns and teachers, catholic schools are still trying to rebuild. In addition to their struggle to get back on their feet after the 1994 Genocide, schools in Rwanda are now facing a new challenge: The country that has used French as a language of instruction since colonialism has recently shifted its policy, requiring schools to teach in English. Unfortunately, most schools are not ready for this change. Students have no access to course books in English. According to Riazat Butt (2011), School libraries are still poor and the few books available are only in French. There is therefore an urgent need for schools to acquire books and other didactic materials in English. Catholic secondary schools and the Catholic University of Save in the Butare Diocese, Southern Rwanda, determined to continue their tradition of providing a strong education to their students, have approached Books for Africa to assist them in acquiring one or two containers of books and other didactic materials in English. These schools need your help and donations, it adds.

In Uganda, the gently used, rescued books have enhanced the lives of students in many low income school Sub - Counties, alternative schools, and special education programmes throughout Illinois. Every year, SCARCE, an organization which operates within Catholic Church, participates in the Catholic Charities Back to School Fair. Its goal is to provide a good selection of books so that each child can choose one of two books of interest. At this event, SCARCE also provides as many dictionaries (English and Spanish) as possible. At the 2009 Catholic Charities Back-to-School fair, SCARCE gave out over 11,000 books to the 1,147 families (5,688 individuals) who attended. Attendance was up by 1,400 from the previous year. All teachers are welcome to check out our Book Rescue as a free resource for your school. Our shelves display over 25,000 books. Around the world, the donated books & supplies have also found new homes in schools, orphanages and libraries in 25% of the countries around the world - including Kenya, China, India, Lithuania, Columbia, Honduras, Costa Rica, Uganda and many more. SCARCE collects the books and partners with other

organizations that ship and deliver them (Regnerus, 2007). Many of the books come from schools that replace their books, so most of the textbooks are in "classroom quantities" -- the books are rescued from one school and provided for another school. There are also "library books" donated by schools, libraries, and the general public, adds Regnerus (2007).

In Kenya, however, there exist no clear programmes by the Catholic Church as far as contribution of instructional materials are concerned. The church relies, more so on international donors to fulfill this. Such are the St. Dorothy's parishioners' that first contribution to St. Massimo Parish in the Diocese of Meru, Kenya, which resulted in the construction of a new church and a Catholic school named after the Glendora parish, whose congregation learned to love Kenyan children through their direct contact with Father Bernard Njeru. A bond was established between the African priests and St. Dorothy's congregation, and in 2006 they started sponsoring students through the Kenyan Children's Project Meru. Tuition, books, clothing and food are paid via \$360-per-year sponsorships. About 400 children have been sponsored to date, and five have already gone to college. A huge container parked behind the church is slowly being filled with books, dental chairs, computers, tables and school supplies, all donated. Once a year the whole community gathers for a potluck, the year's largest fundraiser to support families in Kenyans (Oduor & Nyamu, 2012).

Wabwoba and Simatwa, (2010) in their study, Contribution of the Quaker church to management of public secondary schools in Bungoma East district, Kenya: Analytical assessment, carried an in depth analysis on the contribution of the Quaker Church in management of public secondary schools in Bungoma East, with special emphasis on the staffing of public secondary schools, enhancement of school discipline, motivational mechanisms the Quaker Church have in place for effective management of public secondary schools; and the challenges of the Quaker Church face in the management of public secondary schools in Bungoma East District. The results indicated that the Quaker Church did not intervene in staffing related issues as indicated by 20 (91%) principals who pointed out that Quaker church did not intervene in staffing against 2 (9%) principals who said that they intervened. Only 4 (18%) BOG Chairpersons approved while 14 (64%) disapproved and 4 (18%) were undecided. As for PTA Chairpersons, only 1 (5%) approved while 21 (95%) disapproved. On the part of teachers, it emerged that 13(12%) teachers agreed that the Quaker church intervened in staffing matters while 94(88%) disagreed. The results also revealed that the Quaker church's contribution to staffing was low as indicated by only 9 (41%) who perceived it as good principals. The other principals 7 (32%) and 6 (27%) on the other hand indicated its contribution to staffing as satisfactory and poor respectively. The study did not carry out any research on the Contributions of the Catholic Church, while at the same time; fell short of finding out the Church's contributions on the appointment of school administrators and infrastructural resources.

Mosomi (2008), in his study, Religious sponsors and emerging conflicts in the management of public secondary schools in Nandi South Sub-County, concentrated on the conflicts between sponsors and the sponsored schools, with special emphasis on the possible sources of the conflicts and the relevant strategies to address them. The study was carried out in Nandi South Sub-County which does not share geographical and cultural characteristics with Kisii Central Sub-County. The study found out that, (a) the church believed that it was the sole owner of schools and that the management of schools to be tuned towards church doctrines, but some of the principals came from other churches, hence the conflicts. (b) The church wanted to have complete roles in appointment of principals and every aspect of the school management but the government has its policies of the same. Mosomi's (2008) study dealt generally with religious sponsors and did not focus on the Catholic Church's contribution to financial and infrastructural resource development in public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County which was the subject of this study as the knowledge gaps that needed to be filled.

Onderi and Makori (2013), in their study, Challenges in leadership and management of church sponsored secondary schools in Kenya: Examining the relationship between principals and sponsors, did the Challenges in leadership and management of church sponsored secondary schools in Kenya, with special emphasis on examining the relationship between principals and sponsors, which was also based on conflicts between the sponsors and the school administration; which included undue interference with the running of the schools, harassment and intimidation of the principals and also promoting unnecessary transfer of school principals. Overall Seventh Day Adventist church leads in the issues of undue interference. For instance, 3.7% and 10% for SDA Church, illustrating a proportion between the total sample (81) and the total amount of comments (30) made on issues affecting principals. The percentages are small but still raise concerns regarding the issues cited. It also revealed that SDA church and Catholic Church sponsors have been associated with the issues of harassment and intimidation. Seventh-Day Adventist Church and Catholic Church sponsors have been cited in all three issues, District Education Board (DEB) in two, while Church of God (COG), Lutheran and African Inland Church (AIC) have each been cited in one. The interference include wanting the children to adopt the church''

programmes, for example the SDA insisting that the students do manual work on Sundays. The study also did not deal with the contributions of the Catholic Church in terms of financial resource, instructional resources, infrastructural development and appointment of school administrators.

Mwangangi (2000) in his study, *The Role of The Catholic Church In Provision of Education In general and in particular Primary Education: A Case Study of Machakos Catholic Diocese, Kenya*, intended to carry out a case study of Machakos Catholic Diocese role in the provision of education in general and in particular primary education with a view of finding out what role the Catholic church has done and how its work can be strengthened, so that the church can achieve its basic mission of evangelizing through education. The study concentrated in the role of Catholic Church in provision of education in general and in particular primary education; the implementation of Education Act 1968, affected the role of the Catholic Church in the provision of education; analysis of the Diocese Education policy and suggest ways in which it can be strengthened to enable the church play a more active role in provision of Education and to find out what Catholics in Diocese of Kisii wish would be the role of their Church in provision' of Education. Findings indicated that:

1. Towards participation in schools, the Catholic Diocese of Machakos has helped in setting up and sponsor 352 primary schools within the Diocese out of a total of 1346 primary schools. This represents 26% of the total number of primary schools within the Diocese, which covers Machakos and Makueni Districts. Twenty-six (26) per cent is far below the expectations of the Catholic faithfuls and priests who feel very strongly that the diocese should be hundred (100) per cent involved in provision of Education.
2. On secondary education the Catholic Diocese of Machakos has helped set up and sponsor 91 secondary schools out of a total of 252 secondary schools within the Catholic Diocese of Machakos. This represents thirty-six (36) per cent of the secondary schools and is far below expectations of Catholics in the Diocese who are for hundred (100) per cent involvement of the church in provision of education. The argument for Churches involvement in secondary education is that, the secondary schools available within the Diocese are not adequate to cater for the large number of primary school leavers, given the fact that Nationally, it is only about forty-eight (48) per cent of all primary school leavers each year who manage to get places in form one.

The study did not focus on the contribution of the Catholic Church to provision of instructional resources, financial resources, appointment of school administrators and infrastructural resources, which are factored in management of schools as measured by Management Quality Index. This study therefore, set out to establish the actual contributions of the Catholic Church in the management of public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County, Kenya.

Mabeya and Ndiku (2010) in their study on role of Church sponsor in the management of secondary schools: impact on academic performance and conflict concern in Kenya, viewed the school as a social system with a series of sub-systems within it which interact with each other and the environment. Such school sub-systems include sponsors, teachers, head teachers, Board of ManagementOM, Parent Association, students and support staff. They argue that for the school to achieve its goals and objectives effectively, the subsystems should interact harmoniously. They concentrated on the role of Church sponsor in secondary schools, zeroed in on Impact on academic performance and conflict concerns between the sponsors and the school management in Kenya. The results obtained from the analysis showed that there was a significant relationship between the role of the sponsor in the provision of a conducive learning environment and academic performance. On the roles of the sponsor in school management, the findings revealed that all the church sponsors 97(100%) contributed to the maintenance of religious traditions and church doctrines in schools. The sponsors also concentrated in the provision of teaching learning materials to supplement the efforts of the parents and the government and to enhance curriculum implementation. The sponsors' provision of text books to the schools was given prominence in terms of class readers and reference materials for both teachers and students. This therefore enhanced academic performance of the sponsored schools.. The reviewed studies by Regnerus (2007), focused on the contribution of the Catholic Church in Uganda in terms of provision of a good selection of books so that each child can choose one of two books of interest; but did not deal with the contribution of the Catholic Church to instructional resources in Kisii Central Sub-County.

In England, the posts of Principal, Deputy Principal and Head or Coordinator of Religious Education are to be filled by baptised and practising Catholics. Other Leadership posts that directly affect the Catholic Mission of the school should, wherever possible, be staffed by skilled practitioners who are committed Catholics. All teachers must respect and support the aims and objectives of a

Catholic school (Mbatia and Mureu, 2008). Interview procedures approved by Governing Authorities for teacher recruitment must be open to scrutiny. They must be clear, objective and transparent. Governing Authorities in maintained schools and academies must agree advisory rights for the Diocesan director or their representative and, in maintained schools for the Diocesan director or their representative, in relation to the appointment of teachers at the school. These may be in relation to all appointments at the school or, more usually, to the appointment of Principals and Deputy Principals alone. Whatever advisory rights the Governing Authority confers in maintained schools it must be the same for both the Diocese and LA. The Governing Authority of Independent schools, other than academies, are strongly encouraged to involve the Diocese in all senior appointments (Riazat, 2011).

Governing Authorities should notify the Diocesan director and, for maintained schools the LA, of a vacancy for a Headteacher/Principal or Deputy Headteacher/Principal before taking any action, including appointing an acting Headteacher/Principal or advertising the vacancy. For appointments of Head and Deputy Principals, the Governing Authority will meet to draw up a shortlist of candidates, conduct interviews and make an appointment. The Governing Authority may appoint a selection panel to undertake these functions. These appointments may need ratification by the full Governing Authority (Riazat, 2011). The Governing Authority of a maintained school should be mindful of its statutory responsibilities to advise and consider the views of the LA throughout the process up to ratification of the preferred candidate. In addition, the appropriate Diocesan officer should always be invited to the interview of Heads of Religious Education and school chaplains.

In Uganda, it is argued that it is unacceptable for a person from a parallel faith to head Catholic Schools which belong to Church of Uganda. It is argued that such an attempt would jeopardize the operations and development of the institutions. It cites the Pre-Primary and Post primary Act which was assented to by President Museveni on August 26 2008 stating that there shall be unhindered cooperation between government and stakeholders like foundation bodies especially in the running and management of institutions aided by government. Members of Church of Uganda are not ready to work with outsiders. (Ramadhan, 2011).

In Kenya, the sponsor is involved in the appointment of BOM. According to the Education Act Cap 211, under Section 10, 4. (c), a school sponsor is allowed to nominate four (4) of the ten (10) members of the school Board of Governors during the nomination exercise which is there after presented to the Minister of Education for appointment and to propose the chairman during the inauguration of the new Board for his/her election by the ten (10) members, and who should be ratified by the Minister of Education (Republic of Kenya, 2004). This illustrates the powers given to the sponsor on the management of secondary schools, which at times is misused due to misunderstanding and by the same sponsors willingly due to personal interests, violate.

The Act allows an agreement to be made between the Ministry of Education and the sponsoring churches as regards the rights and responsibilities of the Church sponsor in appointment of school administrators, e.g. principals and their deputies through consultation. This affects the management of public schools where churches that were managers of schools before became sponsors of such schools hence usually dictate terms on who should be appointed to those positions (Republic of Kenya, 2004).

Mosomi (2008), in his study, Religious sponsors and emerging conflicts in the management of public secondary schools in Nandi South Sub-County, concentrated on the conflicts between sponsors and the sponsored schools, with special emphasis on the possible sources of the conflicts and the relevant strategies to address them. The study was carried out in Nandi South Sub-County which does not share geographical and cultural characteristics with Kisii Central Sub-County. The study found out that, (a) the church believed that it was the sole owner of schools and that the management of schools to be tuned towards church doctrines, but some of the principals came from other churches, hence the conflicts. (b) The church wanted to have complete roles in appointment of principals and every aspect of the school management but the government has its policies of the same.

On the other hand, according to Wabwoba and Simatwa, (2010), the Quaker church did not intervene in staffing issues of the principals and deputy principals in Bungoma East District but concentrated more in spiritual nourishment of the students and teachers in the schools they sponsored. It monitored the staffing situations and offered informed opinions wherever they arose.

Kimotho (2008) depicts this region, that is, Kisii, as being known for strong religious stands compared to the rest of Nyanza Province in relation to school sponsorship and expectations from the schools by the sponsors. It has always been realized that lack of proper definition of the role of the sponsor particularly in providing a conducive learning environment has contributed to poor academic performance of some sponsored schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. Today, the idea of sponsorship is understood differently. It consists of maintaining and fostering the religious traditions of the sponsor. In this region, the sponsor always insist that no activity is carried out in the school on the said Sabbath day including academic programmes, for example, examinations, games and sports as well as remedial lessons. Administrators as well must be faithful of the church.

The Bishop is responsible for the total religious education in the diocese, according to the Kenya Episcopal Conference (2000). This is a christian responsibility which the bishop cannot relinquish but which he can and does share. The education Secretary, Assistant Education Secretary for every Sub - County are appointed to be in charge of secondary schools. The Diocese, normally in the person of the Bishop, is the sponsor of all the Catholic schools in his area. The Education Secretary is appointed by the Bishop and represents the diocese in educational matters with the Ministry of education on regional level, with diocesan sponsored schools at local level. The Education Secretary is to ensure that the sponsored school is administered well and to offer needed guidance to both the Principal and teachers when necessary.

The Principal and the deputy Principal are appointed by the Teachers Service Commission after appropriate consultation with the sponsor (consultation – here means agreement in writing between the sponsor and the Teachers Service Commission. No appointment should be made without consultation. Heads of schools and educational administrators need to be aware that authentic authority pre-supposes a spirit of service and a strong sense of responsibility. It means giving their whole attention and dedicating all their working hours to the school. According to Cheruiyot (2008) and Gikandi (2013) some sponsors have been accused of interfering with the schools’ core business by closing down schools indefinitely. In other instances, some have rejected and even evicted Principals posted to schools by the Ministry of Education while some sponsors meddling in schools destabilize the instructive activities in the system. All teachers irrespective of their faith must respect the traditions of the Catholic sponsored school in which they are working. Staff members are expected to work as a team with the Principal and Deputy Principal and participate in all activities of the school. They have to follow regulations set by the Code of Regulations set by the Ministry of Education.

Contrary to other studies that have been conducted on the church sponsorship of secondary schools, which majorly focus on the negative aspects of the sponsor, especially the conflicts created, this study will focus on the positive roles of the sponsor, that is, the Catholic Church with regard to the overall and wholesome development of the sponsored school under special attention to how church sponsors contribute to management of public secondary schools, the extent to which church sponsor contributes to financial management of secondary schools, the challenges faced by Principals while dealing with sponsors in management of church sponsored secondary schools if any, with a view to finding a lasting solutions, as well as significant contribution of the Catholic Church sponsors in infrastructural management of secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County, Kenya.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A conceptual framework is a research tool intended to assist a researcher to develop awareness and understanding of the situation under scrutiny. It has a potential usefulness as a tool to assist a researcher to make meaning of subsequent findings. It forms part of the agenda for negotiation to be scrutinized and tested, reviewed and reformed as a result of investigation (Okumbe, 2009). The study was guided by the conceptual framework and whose operation is displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework on Contribution of The Catholic Church to school instructional resources and school administrators in schools

The conceptual framework (Figure 1) shows that the Catholic Church plays an integral part in the provision of instructional resources and appointment of school administrators. It further shows that the value addition takes various forms, for example, provision of money, materials and advice. This value addition is measured in terms of rating scale on the Provision of Instructional Resources and Appointment of school Administrators. Management of secondary schools is measured by use of Quality Index of the management. In addition the attitude of the Education Secretary is important aspect of the school's overall performance. It therefore means that, if the Catholic Church is effectively involved in the management of Public Secondary school, the school can perform well in Quality index and maintain the good performance over the years, the school should enjoy prudent financial management, the school should have improved and well managed physical infrastructure and lastly the appointment of school administrators namely the Board of Governors, the Principal and the Deputy Principal should be on merit. On the contrary, if the sponsor is ineffective in management of public secondary school, the school will suffer negatively in that – there will be poor academic performance, there will be poor financial management the physical infrastructure of the school will be wasted or managed and lastly, the school administrators may end up being incompetent and inefficient.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive survey design. The study targeted 132 respondents in 32 public Catholic Church sponsored secondary schools within Kisii Central Sub-County. The population comprised of 29 principals, 29 deputy principals, 29 Board of Management chair persons, 29 PA chair persons, 1 Education Secretary, 1 Staffing officer, 1 Sub County Quality Assurance and Standard Officer and 1 Sub County Director of Education. Saturated sampling technique was used to select the respondents. The study used questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis guides to collect data. Face validity of the instruments was determined by the help of experts in the field. Reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained for the questionnaire hence the instrument was reliable for the study. The quantitative data was analyzed using frequency counts, means and regression analysis. Qualitative data obtained through the use of interview schedules was transcribed and analyzed thematically as themes and sub-themes emerged

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Gender of the Respondents

The gender of the respondents was as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	27	94.7
Female	2	5.3
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

The finding in Table 1 reveals that the majority 27 (94.7%) of the respondents were males, and 2 (5.3%) were females. This result implies that the male gender dominates the female counterparts in securing the responsibilities in managing the secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. It was clear that this lacked the one third gender rule as stipulated in the Kenyan Constitution.

Table 2: Qualification of the Respondents

Level of Education	Frequency	Percent
Diploma	2	5.3
B. Ed	13	47.4
M.Ed	5	15.8
MBA	2	5.3
PHD	2	5.3
PGDE	5	15.8
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

Table 2 shows that 2(5.3%) of the respondents had Diploma in education, 13(47.4%) of them had B.Ed, 5(15.8%) of the respondents had M.Ed, 2(5.3%) of them had MBA, 2(5.3%) of them had PhD, 5(15.8%) of them had PGDE. The study finding indicates that 52(47.3%) of the respondent had post graduate studies, and another 52(47.4%) had bachelors in education. Only 6(5.3%) of the respondents had diploma in education. It was evident that the study population was able to tackle the research questionnaire with minimal assistance from the researcher and also they were conversant and had know-how on educational matters.

Table 3: Leadership Experience

Year	Frequency	Percent
3 – 5	6	21.3
6-10	9	26.9
11-14	7	24.1
15 – 20	5	20.3
21 and above	2	7.4
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

The study finding in Table 3 reveals that 6(21.3%) of the respondents had 3-5 years of leadership experience in a Catholic sponsored secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County, 9(26.9%) of them had 6-10 years of leadership experience, 7(24.1%) of the respondents had 11-14 years of leadership experience and 5(20.3%) of them had 15-20 years of leadership experience. Only 2(7.4%) of the respondents had 21years and above in leadership experience in a Catholic sponsored secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. The research result indicates that 23(79.1%) of the respondents had more than 5 years leadership experience. Therefore, this implied that the respondents were able to answer appropriately on the issues addressed by the study and had first-hand information in the education sector in secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County.

Table 4: Type of School

Type of school	Frequency	Percent
Public Day	26	89.5
Boarding	3	10.5
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

According to Table 4, the findings shows that 26(89.5%) of the secondary schools in Kisii Sub - County were public day, and 3(10.5%) were boarding secondary school. The finding indicates clearly that majority were public day schools. It therefore showed that the Catholic Church concentrated more on the public day secondary schools which were situated in rural areas hence more needy.

Table 5: Year of Establishment

Year	Frequency	Percent
1961-1973	5	16.4
1974-1986	0	0.0
1987-1999	9	31.8
2000-2012	15	51.8
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

Table 5 indicates that 5(16.4%) of the schools were established between 1961 and 1973, 9(31.8%) of the secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County were established between 1974 and 1999, while 15(51.8%) of them were established in 2000 – 2012. The

study finding implies that more than half of the secondary schools were established below the year 2000. It is evident that Catholic Church has sponsored many secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County in the early 60s and late 90s. More schools have been sponsored between 2000 and 2012 which was an indication that the church had increased its sponsorship of the schools over the years.

Objective One

The research objective was to establish contribution of Catholic Church to instructional resources in public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County, Kenya.

The management Quality Index was measured as presented in Table 6. This is the indicator for this study's dependent variable which enabled us to carry a correlation.

Table 6: Range of Quality Indices

Management Quality Index	Frequency	Percentage
1	6	20.7
2	18	62.1
3	5	17.2
4	0	0.0
Total	29	100.0

Interpretation of Management Quality Index

- | | |
|-------------------|-----------------|
| 1. Unsatisfactory | 3. Good |
| 2. Very Good | 4. Satisfactory |

Table 6 was derived from the schools' Quality Indices to depict the schools, overall performance as a result of the Church's contribution. The church's contribution on instructional resources was based on items like laboratory equipment, text books and teaching materials e.g. charts models and computers. The Principals were asked to rate on a 5-point rating scale the contribution of the Catholic Church to instructional resources used in public secondary schools that they sponsor. The results were as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: The Catholic Church Contribution to instructional resources in public secondary schools

Mean Ratings	Contribution Index	Frequency	Percentage	Overall mean
1.00 – 1.44	1	10	37.3	
1.45 – 2.44	2	12	40.9	
2.45 – 3.44	3	5	16.4	
3.45 – 4.44	4	2	5.4	
4.50 – 5.00	5	0	0.0	
Total		29	100.0	2.52

Interpretation of contribution Index:

- | | | | |
|---------------|---------|--------------|----------|
| 1 - Very Low | 2 – Low | 3 – Moderate | 4 – High |
| 5 - Very High | | | |

Source: field Data (2015)

Table 7 shows that the overall mean on the church's contribution of instructional resources to schools was 2.52 that was moderate contribution.

Contribution of the Catholic Church to instructional resources in enhancement of secondary school management analysis is shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Contribution of the Catholic Church to Instructional resources and school management Quality Index

		Management of public Secondary Schools
Instructional Resources	Pearson Correlation	.725
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	29

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

From Table 8 it can be noted that the relationship between contribution of the Catholic Church to instructional resources and Quality index was positive and strong ($r = .725, N=29, P < .05$). To estimate the contribution of the Catholic Church, regression analysis was computed and the results were as shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Regression analysis of instructional resources and Quality Index

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					Change of R Square	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.725 ^a	.525	.508	.439	.525	29.861	1	27	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Instructional Resources

b. Dependent Variable: Quality Index

From Table 9, it can be noted that the Catholic Church accounted for 50.8% of variation in Quality Index as signified by the coefficient .508. The other 49.2% was due to other factors that were not subject of the study, for example, teachers attributes, government policy, student characteristics and attitudes. To confirm whether the Catholic Church's contribution was a significant predictor, ANOVA was computed (Table 10).

Table 10: Computation of ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.759	1	5.759	29.861	.000 ^b
	Residual	5.207	27	.193		
	Total	10.966	28			

a. Dependent Variable: QUALITY INDEX

b. Predictors: (Constant), Instructional Resources

From Table 10 it can be observed that the Catholic Church contribution on instructional resources was a significant predictor of school management Quality Index ($(1, 27) = 29.861, P < .05$). To compute the actual contribution, simple regression analysis was computed (Table 4.12).

Table 11. Simple Regression analysis of Catholic Church Contribution to Instructional Resources and School management Quality Index

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	.195	.334		.583	.564	-.491	.880
Instructional Resources	.499	.091	.725	5.465	.000	.311	.686

From Table 4.11, it can be noted that one unit increase in Catholic Church contribution to instructional resources will improve school management index by .499 units. Regression equation therefore is $Y = .195 + .499X$.

Objective Two

The research objective was to establish contribution of Catholic Church on appointment of secondary school administrators in public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub – County

The Principals were asked to rate on a 5-point rating scale the contribution of the Catholic Church to appointment of secondary school administrators in public secondary schools that they sponsor.

The results were as shown in Table 12.

Table 12: The Catholic Church Contribution to appointment school administrators

Mean Rating	Contribution Index	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Mean
1.00 – 1.44	1	0	0.0	
1.45 – 2.44	2	2	5.5	
2.45 – 3.44	3	6	20.9	
3.45 – 4.44	4	9	31.8	
4.50 – 5.00	5	12	41.8	
Total		29	100.0	3.40

Interpretation of contribution Index:

1 - Very Low	2 - Low
3 - Moderate	4 - High
5 - Very High	

Source: Field Data (2015)

Table 12 shows that the overall mean on the Catholic Church’s contribution to appointment of secondary school administrators was 3.40 that was a moderate contribution. To establish the contribution of the Catholic Church to appointment of school administrators in enhancement of public secondary school management quality indices of schools was established for purposes of correlation (as shown in Table 4.7), which was derived from the schools’ Quality Indices to depict the schools’ overall performance as a result of the Church’s contribution.

Contribution of the Catholic Church to appointment of school administrators in enhancement of secondary school management analysis is shown in Table 13.

Table 13: Contribution of the Catholic Church to appointment of school administrators and school management Quality Index

		Management of Public Sec. Schools	
Appointment of School Administrators	Pearson Correlation		.526
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N		29

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

From Table 13, it can be noted that the relationship between contribution of the Catholic Church to appointment of school administrators and Quality index was positive and moderate ($r = .526, N=29, P < .05$). To estimate the contribution of the Catholic Church, regression analysis was computed and the results were as shown in Table 14.

Table 14: Regression analysis of appointment of school administrators and Quality Index

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.526 ^a	.276	.250	.542	.276	10.313	1	27	.003

a. Predictors: (Constant), Appointment of School Administrators

b. Dependent Variable: Quality Index

From Table 14, it can be noted that the Catholic Church accounted for 25.0% of variation in Quality Index as signified by the coefficient .250. The other 75.0% was due to other factors that were not subject of the study, for example, teacher qualification, government interests, student characteristics and attitudes. To confirm whether the Catholic Church’s contribution was a moderate predictor, ANOVA was computed (Table 15).

Table 15: Computation of ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3.031	1	3.031	10.313	.003 ^b
Residual	7.935	27	.294		
Total	10.966	28			

a. Dependent Variable: QUALITY INDEX

b. Predictors: (Constant), Appointment of School Administrators

From Table 15, it can be observed that the Catholic Church contribution was a significant predictor of school management Quality Index ($(1, 27) = 10.313, P < .05$).

To compute the actual contribution, simple regression analysis was computed as shown in Table 16.

Table 16: Simple regression analysis of Catholic Church contribution to appointment of school administrators and school management Quality Index

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
___ (Constant)	.007	.618		.011	.992	-1.262	
1 Appointment of School Administrators	.536	.167	.526	3.211	.003	.194	.878

a. Dependent Variable: Quality Index

Source: Field Data (2015)

From Table 17, it can be noted that one unit increase in Catholic Church contribution to appointment of school administrators will improve school management by .536 units. Regression Equation therefore is $Y = .007 + .536X$. Findings revealed that the sponsors' involvement in appointment of school administrators was moderate.

DISCUSSION

The interview findings showed that indeed the Catholic Church offered support on laboratory equipment. The Education secretary said; “most of the Catholic sponsored schools in Kisii Central Sub - County had received laboratory chemicals, micrometer screw gauge, test tubes, boiling tubes, microscope slides, microscope and vernier calipers for the Science subject practicals from the Catholic Church.” Similar comments were made by the Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officer who said; “majority of the Catholic sponsored schools within Kisii Central Sub - County had received Laboratory chemicals and other laboratory equipment such as Microscope slides and Microscopes to aid in practical lessons, worth about Kshs. 250, 000.” The findings were supported by the document analysis of records held by the schools in question. That included the inventory records for both expendible and permanent goods. In deed the records indicated that the Church supplied science laboratory chemicals and microscopes in 13 secondary schools worth Ksh. 250, 000 to support the teaching of science subjects.

Despite the fact that the Ministry through Free Secondary Education provides money for laboratory materials, in most cases, they are inadequate because students undertake practicals which are demanding based on the curriculum requirements. As a result principals of schools request stakeholders to supplement the government effort in provision of the laboratory equipment. This is in consistent with requirements of the basic education Act 2013 which requires that the sponsor should be actively involved in the school development in terms of students' spiritual growth and implementation of the curriculum. This contribution varies from school to school depending on the level of need and interest of the school management. The sponsor can provide the equipment through the BOM or on request by the school administration.

The findings were supported by Neal (2008), who said that in England and Wales, there have been considerable changes to the way the money has been collected to the support of Catholic schools. The money towards the Catholic community in regards to learning materials and supporting schools has risen from 50% to 90% in both England and Wales. Neal however does not specify the actual materials provided by the church to schools. This was contrary to the situation in Kisii Central, in which the Church gave actual materials to schools, as oppose to giving money for their purchase as seen in England and Wales.

Further, the findings show that the Catholic Church contributed text books to the sponsored secondary schools. The qualitative analysis from interview schedules shows that secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County received text books from the sponsors. The Education secretary was reported to have said; “our schools were given over 4000 text books for English literature and Science subjects.” Also the SCDE mentioned; “more than 22 Catholic sponsored schools in Kisii Central Sub - County received text books from their sponsored in the last 5 financial years.” SCQASO said; “in most cases public secondary schools sponsored by Catholic Church has received cash to the tune of about Kshs 500,000.00 from the sponsors for text book materials”.

The findings above from interview schedules confirm the results from questionnaire respondents. It is evident that public secondary schools sponsored by Catholic Church received text book materials from their sponsors. The findings were further supported by the

document analysis of records held by the schools in question. That included the inventory records for expendable goods. In deed the records indicated that the Church supplied text books to about 22 secondary schools in the Sub - County to support teaching and learning processes worth Kshs. 500, 000 from the Catholic Church. In most cases the church received donations from other international friends and these were supplied to the schools straight away. Such effort was also supplemented by parents' contributions as well as book harvesting days. Despite the fact that the Ministry through Free Secondary Education provides money for text books, in most cases, they are inadequate based on the curriculum requirements. As a result principals of schools request stakeholders to supplement the government effort in provision of the text books. This is in consistent with requirements of the basic education Act 2013 which requires that the sponsor should be actively involved in the school development in terms of students' spiritual growth and implementation of the curriculum. This contribution varies from school to school depending on the level of need and interest of the school management. The sponsor can provide the equipment through the BOM or on request by the school administration.

The study finding also agrees with Regnerus (2007) which established that Catholic Church in Uganda was donating books and even dictionaries to schools through its organization known as SCARCE. Further, the Catholic Church contributed teaching material support to the schools in terms of charts, models and computers. The qualitative findings from the interview schedules show that indeed schools from Kisii Central . Sub - County received teaching materials from their sponsors. The Education secretary was reported to have said; "over 15 secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County received more than 100 cartons of charts, 500 computers and 5000 models for the facilitation of learning." The study finding also reported Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officer (SCQASO) said; "it seems most schools in Kisii Central Sub - County had received a good number of computers, boxes of charts and models from sponsors worth about Ksh. 100, 000 to facilitate teaching and learning in schools". That was supported by the document analysis of records held by the schools in question which included the inventory records for expendable goods. In deed the records indicated that the Church supplied charts, model and pens to various schools in the Sub - County to support teaching and learning processes to the tune of about Kshs 100, 000. In addition, it was indicated that various schools had organized fund raising activities and the Church always contributed money for purchase of extra teaching materials, for example, text books and laboratory equipment.

Most of these schools needed the contributions as they were young and upcoming schools and which were generally established in remote and poor neighbourhood, and with very small student enrolment that can support all the needs of the schools. Hence the Catholic Church usually came in handy to assist them with other basic requirements to support curriculum implementation by providing the teaching learning material as this also supplemented the government effort through the provision of FSE funding which in most cases is not adequate. These findings show that public secondary schools received learning materials from their sponsors. The finding of the study confirms Neal (2008) who established that monetary support by the Catholic Community towards learning materials and supporting schools had risen from 50% to 90% in England. However, in Rwanda, regardless of the effort the Catholic Community trying to fund the Catholic schools with instructional materials support most schools libraries are still poor and the few books available are not adequate (Riazat, 2011). Riazat (2011) however does not specify the actual materials provided but this study specifies the materials that the Catholic Church provides to secondary schools. The findings above were confirmed from document analysis that in deed the church supplied more text books than any other instructional material as the church received more text books from international friends who in most cases donated the text books to the church and which were supplied to the sponsored schools. Text books also form a major part in the overall academic development of students as they are used as reference materials and for further reading.

Qualitative data from the questionnaires revealed that 87(79.1%) of the respondents stated that sponsors are capable of doing more for material support. On the other hand 17(15.4%) of the respondents indicated that sponsors were not capable of doing more for material support. This is because the Catholic Church worldwide contributes more to education and medical services. The contribution comes from the Church members who surrender their earnings to the church. They also mobilize funds from developed countries for use in developing countries. The finding concur with Oduor and Nyamu (2012) who established in Kenya every year the Catholic church makes effort to collect books, dental chairs, computers, tables and school supplies which gets to schools. In addition, the study finding is in agreement with Regnerus (2007) which highlighted that in Uganda, through SCARCE, Catholic Church is able to collect books and partners with other organizations to ship and deliver the books to schools.

The Basic Education Act 2013, Section 56 (5) indicates that for public schools sponsored by faith-based organizations, the Chairperson of the Board of Management shall be appointed by the County Education Board in consultation with the sponsor (Republic of Kenya, 2013). Section 56 (7) of The Basic Education Act 2013 adds, that despite subsection (5), a faith-based sponsor who does not make a significant contribution and impact to a school or institution as contemplated under section 2 of the Act shall not be consulted in the appointment of the chairperson of the Board of Management of that school or institution. The qualitative findings indicated that sponsor was involved in appointment of school administrators within public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. The education secretary quoted; “in all our schools, the church has played vital contributions in the appointment of school Principals and the deputy Principals.” Further the SCQASO said; “during the recruitment of the principals and other school administrators we do consult the sponsor before the appointment is affected.” Similar sentiments were made by the Staffing officer; “in collaboration with the sponsor, the appointment of the school administrators have been done always through involvement of both parties, from the Ministry of Education and also with the sponsor.” The finding above reveals that sponsor has been involved in the appointment of the school administrators. This is a great effort since it brings the effort of all the education stakeholders together in charting the needed steps in ensuring that the appointments done are fair and free. Document analysis as contained in the files containing minutes of meetings supported the findings above as there were clear evidence of involvement of the sponsor and consultations in appointment of school administrators between the sponsor and the education officials. These also included the various correspondence files containing letters for communication between the two parties.

The Education Act 2013 recognizes the critical roles played by the various secondary school sponsors in supporting the schools at all levels. It is in this regard that despite the fact that the TSC Act 2012 gives the Teachers’ Service Commission the sole responsibilities of teacher management, there is still the of involving the sponsors as one of the key stakeholders in education in appointment of the various school administrators, which include the principals, deputy principals and the BOM. The Catholic Church is usually invited to be part of the selection panel for Catholic Church sponsored secondary schools in which they are allowed to propose three names for appointment as BOM members by the County Directors of Education. The BOM members sponsored by the church are meant to protect the interests of the sponsor in the sponsored schools in terms of maintaining the church doctrines both at school administration as well as the management levels. The study findings concur with Ouya and Mweseli (2015) who highlighted that the Catholic Church in England has contributed in the staffing of skilled practitioners to the Catholic schools. Further, the findings agree with Riazat (2011) who found out that in England, Governing Authorities should liaise with the Diocesan director for the appointment of school administrators especially the Principal and the deputy Principals in schools. Cheruiyot (2008) and Gikandi (2013) however had issues with some sponsors in Kenya who have been accused of interfering with the schools’ core business by closing down schools indefinitely. In other instances, some have rejected and even evicted Principals posted to schools by the Teachers Service Commission while some sponsors meddling in schools destabilize the instructive activities in the system.

CONCLUSION

The Catholic Church contribution on instructional resources was critical in school management Quality Index which was positive and strong. With increased support, more instructional materials were available to student for instance text books for their continuous reading and reference, thereby assisted to keep learners busy all the times. The contribution included items like laboratory equipment, text books and teaching and learning materials that is. charts, models and computers.

The Catholic Church’s involvement to appointment of school administrators was moderate. The involvement of the Church in appointment was a significant predictor of school management Quality Index. The administrators included the principals, Deputy Principals, teachers, Board of Management and PA members.

The Catholic Church accounted for 50.8% variation in Quality Index for instructional resources and 25% for appointment of school administrators hence the Church contributed significantly to instructional resources and less significantly on appointment of school administrators.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The sponsor should be conversant with the syllabi offered in the public institutions and provide only those text books that are relevant to the system of education.
- ii. The sponsor, while exercising its role in appointing of school administrators should be more open and practice meritocracy for the sake of picking the best and encourage hard work for better recognition.

- iii. The church should incorporate competent educationists who are well versed with educational management in its school programmes to replace the less informed nominees on school boards of management for assured success.

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